

World Café Dynamic: active learning to address Quality Tools

Lucio Garcia Veraldo Junior^{1,2}, Cristiano Jesus^{3,4,5}

¹ Universidad Federal de São Paulo, Brazil.

² Infinity Academy 3D, Brazil.

³ CiTin – Centro de Interface Tecnológico Industrial, 4970-786, Arcos de Valdevez, Portugal

⁴ ADiT-Lab, Instituto Politécnico de Viana Do Castelo, Rua Escola Industrial e Comercial Nun'Álvares, 4900-347, Viana Do Castelo, Portugal

⁵ ALGORITMI Research Center, School of Engineering, Production and Systems Department, University of Minho, 4800-058, Guimarães, Portugal

Email: lucio.veraldo@infinityacademy3d.com.br, cristiano.jesus@citin.pt

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Abstract

Operational Excellence is a fundamental pillar for the competitiveness of industries and services, promoting process optimization and waste elimination. In the context of higher education, the adoption of active methodologies enhances learning and the practical applicability of theoretical concepts. This study presents a didactic experience based on the World Café dynamic to address the Seven Quality Tools, providing students with an in-depth and interactive understanding of quantitative waste analysis, project management, and decision-making based on indicators. The World Café was employed to stimulate knowledge exchange and co-creation of solutions, allowing participants to move between different discussion groups and explore content from multiple perspectives. The results demonstrated that the methodology fostered greater engagement and knowledge retention, facilitating the understanding of quality tool applications in continuous process improvement. Additionally, the approach enabled students to identify real improvement opportunities and propose technological solutions grounded in scientific principles, bridging theory and practice. This experience reinforces the potential of active methodologies in teaching Operational Excellence applied to Technological Innovation, highlighting that the use of interactive dynamics can be a differentiator in training professionals capable of leading improvement and organizational transformation projects. The research will serve as a foundation for future investigations into the integration of active methodologies in education for industry and services, promoting more effective teaching aligned with market needs.

Keywords: World Café; Quality Tools; Active Learning; Operational Excellence.

1 Introduction

The World Café is a way of creating meaningful dialogues in an organization. Since organizations often need to involve many people in the creation of knowledge, the ambition of the World Café is to reach an area of collective intelligence that has been forgotten in the individualistic cultures of today. The method is based on a belief that there is a field of wisdom which can be reached in groups, but which is usually inaccessible for individuals (Brown & Isaacs, 2005).

Quality tools are important instruments to ensure the continuous improvement of a company's production process. Lobo (2020) states that "quality tools are a first step towards improving process profitability through the optimization of operations." Among the most used tools are the Ishikawa Diagram (known as a herringbone or cause and effect diagram), 5W2H, Histogram, Pareto Diagram, Check Sheet.

Such tools aim to increase efficiency, reduce costs and minimize errors in a process or product. Given this, it is essential to remember that some tools mentioned above do not have a difficult form of applicability as Souza (2018) says "to various quality tools, such as the 5S, CCQ, the 5W2H, cause and effect diagram, can have

practical application, easy deployment and understanding, and lead organizations to a considerable improvement in quality".

Quality management is another field in which several tools for learning and innovation have been created. Exploring ways of integrating the World Café with these tools should be interesting. The World Café and the quality management tools both have an ambition to contribute to profound learning in organizations (Lagrosen, 2019).

This study aims to explore the effectiveness of the World Café methodology in enhancing the teaching and learning process of the Seven Quality Tools within the context of Operational Excellence. Specifically, it seeks to evaluate how this collaborative and dynamic approach supports students in understanding key concepts such as waste analysis, project management, and data-driven decision-making. Additionally, the study examines the extent to which the interactive group format fosters student engagement and encourages the development of practical solutions aligned with continuous improvement initiatives.

2 Active Learning – World Cafe

Active learning has been broadly defined as a type of learning that demands active gathering, processing, and application of information rather than passive assimilation of knowledge (Bonweel & Elison, 1991). This form of learning is well aligned with principles of adult learning, including self-direction, purposefulness, experience-based, ownership, problem orientation, mentorship, and intrinsic motivation (Knowells, 1984).

World Café's have been shown to be useful as a qualitative research method for exploring the viewpoints of many people to create value that is significant. For instance, the method has been used for studying service development and workplace learning in British healthcare (Peddler & Abbot, 2008).

According to Da Silva (2023), a significant feature of the World Café methodology lies in the agility and fluidity among teams, allowing participants to move across multiple groups and examine a given topic from diverse perspectives. As the activity progresses, the initially defined groups begin to diversify, thus ensuring the continuous circulation of ideas and fostering a richer collective understanding.

Brown and Isaacs (2007) emphasize that this methodology enables the connection of various themes around a central topic. This is made possible by the participants' movement across discussion tables, which allows for the formulation of opinions based on the topics previously debated by other groups. Furthermore, according to the authors, active listening to the guiding question, engagement with the perspectives shared by preceding groups, and the ability to connect emerging ideas are essential elements of what is referred to as the "World Café Etiquette," as detailed in Figure 1.

A basic assumption of the World Café is that people have within them the creativity and wisdom that is needed for solving all kinds of problems, even the difficult ones. Discussing in small groups and then spreading the insights to larger groups creates a self-enhancing meaning-creating network. The combination of gathered attention and collective reflection enables the participants to sense patterns, deeper questions and insights into what the heart of the matter is. A kind of wholeness appears in the gap between the participants. World Café's are supposed to be suitable (Brown & Isaacs, 2005)

- for an in-depth exploration of the main challenges and possibilities.
- for sharing knowledge, stimulating innovative thinking and building community.
- for creating a rewarding interaction between speakers and the public.
- if the number of participants is larger than twelve (without any upper limit); and
- if you can spare at least two hours (and up to several days).

Figure 1. World Café Etiquette. Source: <https://www.itcilo.org/methods>

According to Brown (2001), the physical environment selected for welcoming participants must be warm and inviting, with the aim of creating a safe space where everyone feels comfortable. Establishing such an atmosphere is essential to fostering open dialogue and collaboration. Additionally, formulating relevant and thought-provoking questions can yield highly effective outcomes by promoting active participation and engagement. As participants rotate between tables, they are encouraged to contribute meaningfully to the exchange of ideas, key concepts, and thematic insights. This dynamic interaction not only facilitates the emergence of new perspectives but also underscores the importance of listening attentively to those insights and ultimately sharing the collective discoveries with the larger group.

3 Methodology Context

The object of study in this research is the undergraduate course "Operational Excellence," which integrates theoretical foundations and practical applications related to performance optimization in manufacturing and service sectors. The course provides a comprehensive overview of key concepts such as process mapping, value stream analysis, waste reduction, project management, and the use of quality tools for continuous improvement. Students are encouraged to engage in real-world challenges, applying methodologies aimed at increasing productivity, efficiency, and competitiveness.

In this context, the course adopts active learning strategies to deepen students' understanding of operational excellence and technological innovation. By emphasizing experiential learning through problem-solving and teamwork, the course fosters the development of analytical skills and decision-making based on quantitative indicators. One of the main pedagogical approaches applied in this study is the World Café methodology, which is used to teach the Seven Quality Tools interactively and collaboratively. This setup provides a dynamic and inclusive environment that simulates real organizational challenges and prepares students to lead improvement initiatives in their future professional contexts.

The World Café is an easy-to-use participative method to organize and facilitate meetings. It helps create a living network of collaborative dialogue and opens a space for the exchange of ideas (Urbact, 2024):

- **WHAT IS NEEDED?**
 - **Time:** 2 hours
 - **Participants:** 4-5 by table
 - **Material support:** workboard + A4 sheet +pens
 - **Define the roles:** ask one person to be the table host while the others will serve as travelers. The travelers carry key ideas, themes and questions into their new conversations, while the table host welcomes the new set of travelers and facilitates the discussion.
 - **Choose your question(s):** find questions that are relevant to the real-life concerns of the group. You may use the same question for one or more rounds of conversation, or you may pose different questions in each round to build on and help deepen the exploration.
- **WHAT FOR?**
 - **To identify patterns.**
 - **To develop collective knowledge:** at the end of the second or third round, all the tables in the room will be cross-pollinated with insights from prior conversations.
 - **To encourage the emergence of possibilities for action:** by providing opportunities for people to move in several rounds of conversation, ideas, questions, and themes begin to link and connect.
- **HOW TO USE IT?**
 - **Step 1:** Seat people at small Café-style tables or in conversation clusters (optimal number is 4-5).
 - **Step 2:** Set up progressive (at least three) rounds of conversation, approximately 20 minutes each.
 - **Step 3:** Engage questions or issues that genuinely matter to the work of the stakeholder group.
 - **Step 4:** Encourage participants to write, doodle and draw key ideas on their tablecloths and/ or note key ideas on large index cards or placemats in the center of the table.
 - **Step 5:** After completing the initial round of conversation, the table host welcomes a new set of travelers.
 - **Step 6:** After at least three rounds of conversation, initiate a period of sharing discoveries & insights in a whole group conversation.

Figure 2. World Café Method Steps. Source: <https://urbact.eu/toolbox-home/analysing-problems/world-cafe>

4 Results and Discussions

The results obtained from the application of the World Café methodology within the context of the Operational Excellence course reveal valuable insights into students' learning experiences and their understanding of quality management tools. The analysis of responses to the structured questionnaire demonstrates a high level of engagement, comprehension, and critical thinking regarding the use of the Seven Quality Tools in real-world scenarios. This section presents the collected data and discusses the implications of the findings, it highlights how the interactive nature of the World Café contributed to knowledge retention, collaborative learning, and the development of practical skills aligned with continuous improvement and technological innovation.

To deepen the interpretation of student responses, this section also presents graphical representations of the questionnaire results, providing a visual overview of the learning outcomes achieved through the World Café methodology. The graphs illustrate the distribution of responses across each question, allowing for a clearer understanding of student perceptions, levels of knowledge acquisition, and the effectiveness of the methodology in fostering critical reflection on the application of quality tools. These visual data support the qualitative analysis and strengthen the evidence of the methodology's impact on the students' educational experience.

Figure 3. Tools Understood

Figure 4. Stimulated Interest

Figure 5. Learning Collaborative

Figure 6. Practical Application

Figure 7. Interpreted Indicators

Figure 8. Technological Proposals

The analysis of the questionnaire responses administered to students in the Operational Excellence course reveals the effectiveness of the World Café active methodology in the teaching-learning process of the Quality Tools. The strong predominance of favorable responses (option A) across all questions, particularly in questions 1, 2, and 4 with 90% agreement, indicates that students' conceptual understanding was significantly enhanced following the activity. The dynamic and interactive approach facilitated the internalization of theoretical principles and their practical applications, underscoring the potential of active methodologies in fostering deep learning. Question 3, which addressed students' active participation and engagement in group discussions, showed a slight variation, with 70% of students indicating full engagement and 30% reporting partial involvement. While still predominantly positive, this result suggests the presence of varying levels of comfort and initiative among students when engaging in collaborative environments. This observation highlights the importance of complementary strategies aimed at promoting equitable participation and fostering a safe space for idea-sharing, thereby enhancing inclusiveness and collaboration in academic settings.

The analysis of question 5 shows that 80% of students feel capable of applying the Quality Tools in real-world contexts, indicating effective knowledge transfer from theory to practice. Furthermore, the unanimous agreement (100%) in question 6 regarding the overall effectiveness of the methodology confirms its relevance as an innovative and impactful teaching strategy. These qualitative findings support the premise that the World Café methodology promotes not only collective knowledge construction but also the development of essential skills for solving real-world problems, contributing to the formation of more critical, engaged, and technically proficient professionals.

In conclusion, the data derived from the student questionnaire consistently demonstrate that the implementation of the World Café methodology in teaching Quality Tools constitutes an effective pedagogical strategy for advancing operational excellence in academic contexts. By integrating theory and practice through collaborative dynamics, students were encouraged to develop analytical, participatory, and reflective competencies essential for identifying and addressing real-world issues in productive environments. The high rates of positive agreement across all items reflect not only student engagement but also the consolidation of applied knowledge, reinforcing the role of active methodologies as central instruments for innovation in higher education. This study thus contributes to the academic literature on innovative educational practices by showing that experiential learning, supported by interactive dynamics, enhances the formation of professionals equipped to lead continuous improvement and organizational transformation in industrial and service contexts.

5 Conclusion

The present study successfully met its general and specific objectives by exploring the World Café methodology as a tool to enhance student engagement and understanding of the Seven Quality Tools within the discipline of Operational Excellence. The implementation of this active methodology allowed participants to interact dynamically, promoting collaborative learning and the exchange of diverse perspectives on quality-related themes. This approach directly contributed to a deeper comprehension of theoretical content and its practical applicability in real-world organizational settings.

The results obtained through the applied questionnaire reveal a high level of satisfaction and engagement among students. Over 90% of participants strongly agreed that the methodology facilitated the understanding of quality tools, encouraged critical thinking, and improved their ability to interpret performance indicators. Moreover, the unanimous agreement on the opportunity to propose technological solutions grounded in scientific knowledge reinforces the effectiveness of the World Café in aligning academic instruction with market needs.

The study highlights the importance of active methodologies in higher education, particularly in engineering and management disciplines, where theoretical content must be effectively integrated with problem-solving skills. The World Café dynamic proved to be a powerful instrument for knowledge construction, fostering an inclusive and reflective environment that empowers students to become active agents of organizational transformation. This reinforces the pedagogical relevance of structured, student-centered activities in promoting meaningful learning experiences.

For future work, it is recommended to expand the use of the World Café methodology to other topics within Operational Excellence and to conduct comparative studies involving different educational strategies. Additionally, incorporating digital collaboration tools could enhance the scalability and accessibility of the experience, particularly in hybrid or remote learning contexts. The integration of artificial intelligence to support the analysis of group insights and the proposal of continuous improvement initiatives presents a promising avenue for educational innovation and further research.

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